

Reaction of rice accessions to thrips. Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Accession	Field			Greenhouse		
	1992	1993	Reaction ^a	I	II	Reaction ^a
IR62	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
Ptb22	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
Ptb33	1	1	HR	1	1	HR
T235	1	1	HR	3	3.6	R
Afaamwanza 1-1-159	1	1	HR	7	7	S
Ptb19	3	3	R	3	3	R
Ptb20	3	3	R	3	3	R
Pokkall	3	3	R	3	3	R
CO 43	3	3	R	3.6	3.6	R
IET6012	3	3	R	3	3	R
IET6017	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET8833	3	3	R	3	3	R
IR49517-23-2-2-3-3	3.6	3.6	R	7	7	S
RP2271-433	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9702	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9709	3	3	R	7	7	S
IET9727	3	3	R	7.6	7.6	S
T117	3	3	R	7	7	S
T258	3	3	R	3.6	3.6	R
T401	3	3	R	7	7	S
T585	3.6	3.6	R	3	3	R

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible.

susceptible check, were sown randomly alongside the test entries and exposed to natural infestation. Damage was rated twice, at 14 d and 21 d after sowing, on a 0-9 scale where 0 = no damage; 1 =

rolling of terminal third of first leaf only; 3 = rolling of terminal third of first and second leaves; 5 = rolling of terminal half of first, second, and third leaves, yellowing of leaf tip; 7 = rolling of entire

length of all leaves, pronounced yellowing; and 9 = complete plant wilting, yellowing, and scorching. Five of the accessions were highly resistant and 16 resistant (see table).

In the second phase, the 21 resistant accessions were screened twice in the greenhouse. Entries were sown in 10-cm long rows in plastic trays (40 cm × 30 cm × 15 cm), filled 10-cm deep with soil. In each tray, 20 rows were sown in two strips. Ptb33 and TN1 were sown randomly with the test entries.

Each set of entries was replicated three times. Water was added regularly to maintain soil moisture. Leaves infested with *S. biformis* from the stock culture were collected and evenly distributed until the population reached 5 thrips/seedling. Seedlings were covered with a mylar film case with a muslin top. Damage was rated on the 0-9 scale 21 d after infestation. Three of the accessions were highly resistant, nine resistant, and the rest susceptible (see table). ■

Resistance to green leafhopper in rice varieties with different resistance genes

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While identifying sources of resistance to the Tamil Nadu populations of green leafhopper (GLH), *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant), we observed differences in levels of resistance among varieties identified as resistant to GLH at IRRI. Varieties with a known GLH resistance gene or resistance genes and varieties with an unidentified dominant GLH resistance gene were evaluated for damage rating in the seedbox screening test and for their effects on growth of Tamil Nadu GLH populations.

To study varietal reactions, Pankhari 203 with *Glh 1*; ASD7, Tendeng, Rhissa, Sefa, Badal 2, and Chota Digha with *Glh 2*; Chiknal with *Glh 3*; Ptb8 with

glh 4; ASD8 with *Glh 5*; Tapl796 with *Glh 6*; Moddai Karuppan with *Glh 7*; Choron Bawla with *Glh 1 + Glh 2*; Laki 659 with *Glh 3 + Glh 5*; and monogenic varieties Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, ARC10318,

and susceptible check TN1 were sown in 40-cm rows in wooden trays (60 × 45 × 10 cm) with five replications. At 7 d after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15/row, infested with 5-6 second-instar nymphs/

Plant damage rating and population growth of green leafhopper on rice varieties with different genes for resistance^a. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Gene(s) for resistance	Damage rating ^b	Population growth (no.)
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	9.0 a	201.8 ab
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	3.0 b	41.9 efg
Tendeng	<i>Glh 2</i>	2.2 bcd	56.4 d
Rhissa	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.4 de	54.8 d
Sefa	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.8 cde	47.0 def
Badal 2	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.0 e	31.2 ghi
Chota Digha	<i>Glh 2</i>	1.4 de	51.0 de
Chiknal	<i>Glh 3</i>	2.6 bc	50.0 de
Ptb8	<i>glh 4</i>	2.2 bcd	39.6 fg
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	2.6 bc	47.4 def
Tapl796	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.0 e	23.0 i
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	1.0 e	12.4 j
Hashikalmi	One dominant	9.0 a	187.0 c
Ghaiya	One dominant	9.0 a	197.0 bc
ARC10313	One dominant	9.0 a	190.0 bc
Choron Bawla	<i>Glh 1 + Glh 2</i>	1.8 cde	38.8 fgh
Laki 659	<i>Glh 3 + Glh 5</i>	1.0 e	8.6 j
TN1	None	9.0 a	212.8 a

^aMean of five replications. In a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT. ^bDamage scored using SES.

seedling, and covered with a fine fiber glass-mesh cage. Damage was scored on the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)* when TN1 was killed.

Population growth was studied by infesting 30-d-old potted test plants with five pairs of GLH adults. The plants were covered with mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design, replicated five times. Nymphs

Pest resistance— other pests

New ufra-resistant rice lines

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During 1990-93, we tested and selected 29 F_2 populations and their progenies for ufra (*Ditylenchus angustus*) resistance. One hundred twenty-four selected lines of F_3 populations were further evaluated in 1993. Seeds of each of these entries were sown in pots and inoculated with 100 nematodes/plant at 15 d. Entries were scored 6 wk after inoculation based on leaf symptoms of susceptibility (Fig. 1a) and resistance (Fig. 1b-d).

Ten seedlings from each of the entries with resistance symptoms were transplanted for field evaluation from booting to flowering stages. A few seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms were marked with

and adults on each plant were counted 30 d after infestation.

Thirteen varieties, ASD7, Tendeng, Rhissa, Sefa, Badal, Chota Digha, Chiknal, Ptb8, ASD8, Tapl796, Moddai Karuppan, Choron Bawla, and Laki 659, were rated as resistant in the seedbox screening test (see table). Pankhari 203 with *Glh 1* gene, and Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 with a dominant gene, were rated as susceptible. Population

increase was significantly higher on TN1, Pankhari 203, Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 than that on the resistant varieties

Among the GLH resistance genes identified at IRRI, *Glh 1* and a dominant gene in Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 do not confer resistance to GLH populations in Tamil Nadu while varieties with *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, *Glh 5*, *Glh 6*, *Glh 7*, *Glh 1* + *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3* + *Glh 5* do confer resistance. ■

Rice entries with ufra resistance. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Plant type	Entries		
Tall	IR63142-J6-B-1	IR63142-J8-B-2	IR63155-J9-B-1
	IR63174-J1-B-3	IR63188-J8-B-1	IR63188-J8-B-7
	IR63225-J2-B-1	IR63225-J2-B-4	IR63225-J2-B-6
	IR63645-J3-B-8		
Short	IR63174-J1-B-2-3	IR63174-J1-B-3-2	IR63174-J1-B-3-1
	IR63174-J1-B-4-3	IR63174-J1-B-6-3	IR63174-J2-B-4-2
	IR63174-J3-B-1-2		

red cellophane tape to record their survival. After establishment, five plants from each of these entries were dissected to count nematode populations. Rayada 16-06-1 was the resistant check and Habiganj Aman II, the susceptible check.

Sixty-four of the lines survived and flowered successfully. Ten deepwater rice lines (see table) had mild or no resistance symptoms. Seven other resistant entries (see table) were short-stemmed and may be used as resistance sources for rainfed lowland and irrigated rices. These entries had either Bazail 65 or Rayada 16-06 as a resistant parent.

Seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms did not survive to maturity in all of the marked lines, but 91-96% of the secondary tillers that emerged from them survived and flowered successfully. In contrast, neither seedlings with primary infestations nor

secondary tillers of susceptible varieties survived. Nematode numbers were 0-101/plant in resistant entries and 141-3280 in the susceptible ones. Rayada 16-06-1, however, did not have any symptoms or nematodes in this experiment. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

Twelve new rice varieties released for Orissa State, India

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The Orissa State Subcommittee recommended the release of 12 new rice varieties, developed by OUAT, for commercial cultivation in the state. Badami (OR164-5), Nilagiri (OR163-104), Khandagiri (OR811-2), and Ghanteswari (OR377-85-6) are adapted to rainfed and irrigated upland ecosystems; Birupa (OR253-2), Meher (OR526-2008-4), Samanta (OR487-30-3) and Bhanja (OR443-80-4), four midseason varieties, are recommended for irrigated

Symptoms of ufra disease on rice leaves. Susceptible: splash pattern chlorosis (a); resistant: discrete or rounded chlorotic lesion (b, d), elongated chlorotic lesion (c).